

E COMMERCE ADOPTION: EXPERIENCED BENEFITS BY SMES CREATIVE INDUSTRIES IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

E commerce technology present unique opportunities and challenges for modern business. Not only for big firms but also SMEs can get benefit from adopting the e commerce technologies. Participation of SMEs creative industry needs to be ensured in order to use the full potential of e commerce technologies. The purpose of this research are to identify the benefits to adoptions of e commerce technologies in the view point of group SMEs creative industries. This research used a quantitative approach with survey method. In general, the findings designate that the SME creative industries have experienced numerous benefits from adopting e comerce technologies. the most significant benefits from adopting e commerce technologies are: Improved relationships with business partners, Improved productivity of the managers, Improved distribution channels, Support for strategic decision making by managers, Increased cost reduction.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The development of information technology provides great benefits in almost all fields of life including in business field. Information technology in business affects almost all business activities. One of the information technology which created for businesses is e-commerce. E commerce can be briefly defined as a form of business activity and carried out by utilizing electronic data through internet and the World Wide Web (WWW) [1]. E commerce changes the way and paradigm of the community on how businesses are carried out, managed and communicated [2]. The use of e-commerce is not only merely a place to sell, but has become an important ecosystem for Indonesian business people to start and develop their businesses.

E commerce is one form of information technology development which specifically created for business activities although in its development, it is possible to be used for non-business activities. The benefits of e commerce are very large and provide great opportunity for a company to expand its business. E commerce technology also allows the opening of new opportunities in business. E commerce changes the way and paradigm of the community how businesses are carried out, managed and communicated [2]. The use of e-commerce is not only merely a place to sell, but has become an important ecosystem for Indonesian businessmen to start and develop their businesses.

The use of e commerce for the business world has many advantages, some research results showed that e commerce is able to increase sales, develop relation of distribution and improve service to customers [3,4,5,6]. Thus, the implementation of e commerce will bring positive impact for business and economic development.

Other benefits of e-commerce technology implementation are reducing operational costs, improving customer service, increasing communication, and expanding business network [7,8,9,10]. These benefits

cover the overall business activities within the company so that the role of e-commerce technology is very broad and comprehensive. The advantages of implementing e-commerce technology depend on the level of its implementation. The deeper and broader the level of e-commerce implementation, the greater the potential profit gained.

Although it has great benefits, the use of e-commerce in SMEs in Indonesia is still not optimal yet. Based on a survey conducted by Deloitte in 2015 it was found that only 9% of SMEs businesses had applied information technology thoroughly or can be categorized as advanced. Then, it was still based on the results of the survey, 18% of SMEs belong to the middle category in terms of information technology implementation, as much as 37% was in the basic category and the rest was 39% in the offline business category or it did not use information technology at all.

The data above were of course inversely proportional to other the statistical data which showed that the potential of Indonesia in utilizing information technology. The data described that in 2017, internet users in Indonesia were as many as 143 million people or more than 50% of the total population (Association of Indonesian Internet Service Providers). The data showed that the potential use of information technology in Indonesia was not used optimally yet, especially in the SMEs sector. Based on those data above, comprehensive measures are needed to increase the level of e-commerce implementation in Indonesia. The purpose of this research is to explore more about the advantages which gained from the e-commerce technology implementation so that it will provide a broader perspective on the implementation of e-commerce technology in Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Creative Industries Sector

Small and medium micro enterprises (SMEs) are a business sector which until now has a very significant contribution to the economy of a country. There are many versions regarding the definition of SMEs. But in general, the definition of SMEs can be seen from 3 perspectives: international point of view, national perspective and business point of view [11]. In Indonesian context, one of the definitions of SMEs is described in Law No.20, year 2008. According to Law No. 20, year 2008, SMEs were distinguished based on the value of their assets. Micro Business is a business which has a maximum net worth of Rp. 50,000,000 and it does not include land and building for business or has annual sales of Rp. 300,000,000. Furthermore, Small Business was a business which has the following criteria: (1) net wealth more than Rp. 50,000,000 up to a maximum of Rp. 500,000,000 excluding land and buildings for business; and (2) have annual sales results which were more than Rp. 300,000,000 up to a maximum of Rp. 2,500,000,000. Meanwhile, Medium Business is a business entity that has the following criteria: (1) net worth of more than Rp. 500,000,000 up to a maximum of Rp. 10,000,000,000 and not including land and business premises; and (2) have annual sales results of more than Rp. 2,500,000,000 up to a maximum of Rp. 50,000,000,000.

The general definition of SMEs can bring an idea of the extent of the SMEs' scope in Indonesia. One of the SMEs' sectors which most contributes to foreign exchange is creative industry sector. According to the Creative Economy Agency (BKRAF) of the Republic of Indonesia, the creative industry in Indonesia is divided into 16 sub-sectors, namely: culinary, fashion, craft, television and radio, publishing, architecture, application and game developers, advertisement, music, photography, performing arts, product design, fine arts, interior design, film and visual communication design.

Based on some data released by BKRAF (2017), in 2015, the creative industry sector contributed 852 trillion IDR of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) or 7.38% toward the national economy. Whereas in terms of employment, the creative industries sector in 2015, there were 15,959,590 labours. The greatest of economic potential of the creative industrial sector makes this sector must be continued to be developed and encouraged so that it would be able to develop and compete with industries from other countries.

E Commerce and Benefit for SMEs

E Commerce is a process of buying and selling products electronically by consumers and from companies to companies with computers as media for some business transaction [12]. Media which can be used in e-commerce activities is internet. Understanding of e-commerce can be seen from three aspects, namely trade (commerce), business function and collaboration. Based on those three aspects, e-commerce can be defined as the application of telecommunication network technology (telecommunication network) to conduct business transaction, exchange information and maintain relationship with consumers before, during and after the transaction process [13,14].

The classification of e-commerce is generally based on the nature of the transaction. E commerce classification is divided into this following parts: Business to Consumer (B2C), Business to business (B2B), Consumer to Consumer (C2C), Peer-to-peer (P2P) and Mobile Commerce (M -Commerce) Each type has different function and objectives but generally has same outline [12].

The function and purpose of revolutionary e commerce technology will be very useful if they applied to small and medium enterprises or SMEs. SMEs which have some limitation can use e commerce technology to overcome the weaknesses that they have and can also be used to open new and bigger opportunities. Through e commerce, it will open opportunities for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) to market and develop business network throughout the world. For this reason, the owners or bussinessmen of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are required to be part of the global community by utilizing information technology, especially e commerce, if they do not follow the development of information technology, they will be far left behind and lose in competition [15].

III. METHOD

This study applied a quantitative approach with Survey method. The instruments in data collection technique were questionnaires which designed according to research need. The type of question in the questionnaire was closed ended question. Closed ended question was used to determine the type of business activities that had applied e commerce technology and also to find out the advantages gained in the application of e commerce technology. The population in this study were all SMEs in the creative industry which were in Surakarta, Yogyakarta and Semarang. The total number of pollulation were 3460 SMEs in creative industries sector. Then, the sampling technique which used was proportionally random sampling. Based on the sampling technique, the samples in this study were 300 SMEs in the creative industry sector in Surakarta, Yogyakarta and Semarang. The data in this study were primary data and then the data was processed by analyzing the quantitative descriptive data to give clear meaning and description of the data collected in accordance with the objectives of research.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study were presented in several parts in accordance with the research objectives. In the first part, the profile of the respondents, in the second part was about the amount of expenditure per month which spent on internet need, the third was the type of business activities which had implemented e commerce technology in the business activities and the last part was about the description of benefits obtained by respondents in the use of e commerce technology.

Profile of Respondents

Overall, the questionnaire was distributed to 300 units of creative industry or SMEs which located in 3 cities (Surakarta, Yogyakarta and Semarang). The profile of respondents in this study are as follows:

TABLE 1. Respondents profile

No.	Data responden	Frequency	Percent
1.	Role of respondents		
	Owner	245	81,67%
	CEO	31	10,33%

Manager	22	7,33%
IT Manager	2	0,67%
Total	300	100%
2. Gender		
Male	215	71,67%
Female	85	28,33%
Total	300	100%
3. Internet implementation time		
Less than 1 year	15	5,00%
Between 1-5 years	89	29,67%
Between 6-10 years	105	35,00%
More than 10 years	91	30,33%
Total	300	100%

Based on the results of the study, as much as 81.67% of respondents were business owners, then successively the positions of respondents were 10.33% as CEOs, 7.33% were managers, and the rest or 0.67% were IT manager. The gender group in this study consisted of 72% men and 28% women. As much as 35% of respondents had held the position between 6-10 years, 29.67% of respondents had run their positions between 1-5 years, as much as 30.33% of respondents had held positions for more than 10 years and 5% of respondents had held their positions for less than 1 year.

The Age of Internet Usage and The Costs Spent For Internet Need

Based on the data of this research, as much as 40.67% of firms had used internet in their business activities between 4-6 years, then as much as 31% had applied internet to their business between 1-3 years, 16% used internet in their business activities more than 7 years and the rest or 16% of respondents answered that their new companies used internet in business activities for less than 1 year.

The average cost for internet need which issued by firms for one month was as follows: as many as 37% of respondents in one month, they spent on internet need less than 1 million rupiah, then 43.67% spent between 1- million 3 million rupiah, 15.33% spent 3-5 million rupiah and the rest, as much as 4% of respondents spent more than 5 million rupiah in a month for internet need. In detail, the age of internet usage and the average distribution for internet need for a month can be seen in figure 2 below.

FIGURE 1. (a) The duration of internet use and (b) the average cost in a month

The Types of Business Activities Which Used E commerce

Respondents were given seven choices of main business activities in SMEs. The seven choices included: payment, finding new distributors / customers, receiving orders, internal communication, external communication, searching information, marketing and advertising. Based on the results of the study, 100% of respondents answered using e commerce in searching information, then 87.67% of respondents used e commerce for marketing and advertising activities, 77% used e commerce for internal communication activities, 71% used e commerce for receiving orders, 59.67% of respondents used e-commerce for external communication activities, 23.67% used e-commerce for distribution / new customers and finally 10.33% of respondents used e-commerce for payment activities.

FIGURE 2. Types of business activities that have implemented e commerce

Based on the results of the study, they showed that the majority of business activities which applied e commerce technology were still mostly in basic and simple activities. E commerce technology was not used for more sophisticated activities. Searching information activities included searching for new distributors and consumers, external and internal communication were examples of business activities which can be categorized at a simple level. Almost all respondents did not use e commerce technology for more advanced activities, such as data analysis, forecasting and so on. The results of this study were in line with research (Abid, Rahim, and Scheepers), the results of the study found that the majority of e commerce technology was only used for simple activities. This research also confirmed that in the SMEs sector, it still does not utilize e commerce technology comprehensively and it is only used in certain activities [16].

Benefits Gained From The Implementation of E Commerce Technology

At this stage, respondents were given 5 choices of answer regarding to the benefits gained in implementing e-commerce. The choices of answer which submitted by respondents included: reducing operating costs, increasing business network, increasing sales, improving good communication and improving service to customers. The results showed that the majority of respondents or as much as 83.33% got benefit from increased sales through applying e commerce technology, then 70% of respondents experienced an increase in the development of business network, 66.7% of respondents got advantage in form of improved communication, 32, 33% of respondents could reduce operating costs and by 31, 67% of respondents got benefit in improving the quality of service to customers by implementing e-commerce technology.

FIGURE 3. Benefits gained by using e commerce technologies.

The results showed that the majority of respondents got benefit from increasing sales through e-commerce implementation. While in term of customer service, it was only experienced by a few respondents. This was in line with previous research finding where the majority of business activities that implement e-commerce were simple business activities so that the benefit obtained were only in form of simple benefits. More comprehensive and more fundamental benefits, such as the development of innovation and the availability of accurate data cannot be felt by respondents. This finding was in line with research conducted by (Khan, 2016; Franco, Regi, 2016; Molla, 2004) where the benefits gained in implementing e-commerce were in accordance with the level of e-commerce technology implementation. In order to obtain greater and more fundamental benefits, a gradual and continuous process was needed which started from implementation to operation.

The finding in this study also confirmed the results of research from Abid, Rahim, and Scheepers (2011) which emphasized on the reduced production and operational costs of company. The benefits gained from implementing e-commerce as expressed by (Kuzic, Fisher, Shollary 2002) were not found in this study due to differences in the level of maturity of e-commerce technology implementation.

V.CONCLUSION

The majority of respondents had begun to implement information technology in their business between 4-6 years of 40.67%, then between 1-3 years was as much as 31%, more than 7 years of 16% and the rest was less than 1 year with a percentage of 12.33 %. In term of costs which spent for information technology need, as much as 37% of respondents in one month, they spent for internet need less than 1 million rupiah. Furthermore, 43.67% of respondents in one month, they spent fund for internet need as much as 1-3 million rupiah. A total of 15.33 respondents in a month, they spent 3-5 million rupiah for internet need and the rest, as much as 4% of respondents spent more than 5 million rupiah in a month for internet need.

All respondents or as much as 100% used e commerce for searching information, then 87.67% of respondents claimed to use e commerce for marketing and advertising activities, 77% used e commerce in internal communication activities, 71% used e commerce for receiving orders, 59.67% of respondents used e-commerce in external communication activities, 23.67% used e-commerce for distribution /looking for new customers and finally 10.33% of respondents used e-commerce for payment activities.

In term of the benefits obtained from the implementation of e commerce technology, the majority of respondents or 83.33% received benefits in form of increased sales by applying e commerce technology, then 70% of respondents experienced an increase in business network development, 66.7% of respondents got benefit from an increase of fluency in communication, 32.33% of respondents can

reduce operating costs and by 31, 67% of respondents got the benefit from improving the quality of service to customers through implementing e commerce technology.

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